

FAQs

Frequently Asked Questions about the RDA
Knowledge Base

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1. Using the RDA Knowledge Base

Question

What is the RDA Knowledge Base?

Answer

The Knowledge Base is a portfolio of applications, including the ones listed below. Together, the goal of these services are to ensure the high quality, usefulness, maintenance, and sustainability of RDA outputs:

- **RDA Discovery:** Discovery of RDA Outputs, Supplementary Materials, and Web Resources of interest to the community
- **RDA Graph:** a comprehensive database of RDA- and related outputs;
- **RDA Publisher:** Curated Publication of RDA-related resources - with extended metadata and linked into the RDA Graph
- **RDA Annotator:** Annotation of web resources that are of interest to the community - e.g. identified during landscape analysis and research

When should I refer to the Knowledge Base, and when to the RDA website?

Refer to the Knowledge Base for e.g.:

- RDA- & related outputs: e.g. searching, browsing, and filtering for e.g. certain types of outputs, topics, Working Groups, and more;
- Helpdesk for WGs: e.g. practical guidelines; standards; metadata schemas;
- Annotation of web based resources,

The RDA Website is particularly useful for e.g.:

- RDA-related news & events;
- Community and group discussions;
- detailed information about RDA policies, governance, activities etc.

Are the outputs on the Knowledge Base and RDA website harmonised?

All outputs found on the RDA Website are harvested by the Knowledge Base. In addition, the Knowledge Base includes supplementary materials not found on the RDA Website, e.g. related, RDA-external standards, vocabularies, and outputs.

Is the Knowledge Base developed and maintained by the RDA?

Although the Knowledge Base is developed in close collaboration with the RDA, it is an independent output of the [RDA TIGER Project](#), and the RDA takes no responsible for its use and contents (see RDA TIGER Disclaimer)

How can I ask questions or provide feedback?

Click the help icon at the bottom right of the Knowledge Base and fill in the form to create a ticket with our Helpdesk.

What credentials and authentication is supported by the Knowledge Base?

The Knowledge Base currently supports authentication through your Google or ORCID accounts. Other common platforms will be added in the future

2. RDA Discovery

Question

Why can't I apply multiple filters from the same category? For example, selecting multiple Working Groups

Answer

RDA Discovery works using Elasticsearch, and applies filters to results as soon as these are selected. Once a filter is applied, e.g. a particular RDA Pathway, all filters where this Pathway does not apply are removed from view. This is done to help users select meaningful filters (that do not return zero results). If a certain filter does not yield the desired result, try applying a more generally applicable one, or use the free text search.

How can I see more outputs associated with filtered results

The Dashboard views are different views of the same search or filtered results. The Results view shows all results (outputs and/or annotations) found using the filters applied in the Dashboard view. Note that filters can also be changed while in the Results view.

3. The RDA Publisher

Question	Answer
Why deposit to Zenodo using the RDA Publisher?	The RDA Publisher prepares materials for automated deposit to Zenodo (or to other long-term repositories) together with extended metadata, and by linking resources to the RDA Graph
Why publish to Zenodo ?	Zenodo is an open and flexible repository for research papers, datasets, software, and other materials. All RDA outputs are required to be published in one of their two Zenodo Communities .
How to deposit using the RDA Publisher?	Go to the RDA Publisher , log in using your Google or ORCID account, fill in the metadata, and drag the files to be deposited on the second tab, before hitting “Submit data”. Drafts can be saved before publishing using the “Save” button.

4. The RDA Annotator

Question	Answer
Who can view my annotations?	Anyone using the Annotator can view your annotations, however certain fields like “Notes,” are only visible to you.
Where do my annotations get stored?	Annotations are stored in the RDA Graph database. Further details about this can be found in the RDA Annotator Guidelines, section 3.3.
Can I browse, edit, or delete my annotations?	This functionality is being developed, and will be available soon.

research data sharing without barriers

rd-alliance.org